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Anion Exchange Studies of Metal Ions in Aqueous NH₄SCN-DMSO Mixed Solvent Systems

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DOWEX macroporous MSA-1 resin has been used to obtain rapid exchange equilibria. The distribution coefficients of Cr(III), Fe(III), In(III), Hg(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Tl(I) and Ag(I) have been measured by batch process and using radiotracer technique. These measurements have been made in different concentrations (0.1M-5.0M) of aqueous ammonium thiocyanate and in different volume percentages (0-80) of dimethyl sulfoxide at overall one molar concentration of ammonium thiocyanate solution. The effect of DMSO in mixed solvent systems has been studied.

DMSO is a useful solvent for ion exchange studies because it shows some specific selectivities which have not yet been explained. It has high dielectric constant and a strong solvating tendency for metal ions. Numerous studies have therefore been made in DMSO-HCl^{1,2} and DMSO-HNO₃^{3,4} systems. Ammonium thiocyanate is a strong complexing agent which forms a large number of complexes with metal ions. It will be interesting to replace these ligands by thiocyanate in these studies. The preferential uptake of metal-DMSO or metal-thiocyanate complex by the resin opens a new interest. Turner *et al*⁵ investigated the behaviour of some 3d transition metals on Dowex-1 resin in KSCN solutions. Some of the metal ions could not be eluted from the column during the separation. Then some other workers tried NH₄SCN-HCl^{6,7} media using weakly basic⁸ and cellulose⁹ resins. Recently Singh and Tandon¹⁰ studied the anion exchange behaviour of some metal ions in thiocyanate-organic solvent mixed systems. They used acetone, methanol or ThE as organic solvent. As far as we are aware no anion exchange study has been reported in aqueous thiocyanate-DMSO mixed solvent system. We have therefore tried to investigate the ion exchange and DMSO behaviour in

these mixed solvent systems. Some interesting separations have also been developed using distribution data.

Experimental

Apparatus and Chemicals : Na(I) (Tl) well type scintillation counter was used for gamma countings of Cr(51), Mn(54), Co(58), Fe(59), Zn(65), Ag(110m), In(114 m) and Hg(203). Beta countings of Cd and Tl were done on a Geiger M Counter.

The macroporous resin (Dowex MSA-1), 20-50 mesh, Cl-form was received from Sigma Chemical Co.(USA) as a gift. All metal sulphates or nitrates were of BDH AnalaR grade. Metal tracers were collected from BARC, Trombay (India). The DMSO was from J. T. Baker Co., Phillipsburg. The ammonium thiocyanate was of BDH AnalaR grade.

The resin was converted into thiocyanate form by treating it with 5M NaOH followed by 20% KSCN solution for 3 days with intermittent shaking. The resin was then washed with water and then dried. The ion exchange capacity was found 3.9 meq/g.

The Kd values were determined by batch process. In this process the exactly weighed 0.5 g resin were added into 50 ml stoppered conical flasks which contained 2 × 10⁻² meq metal ion in 10 ml solvent mixtures. The content was allowed to stand for 16 hours with intermittent shaking. The resin was filtered and 2 ml of the filtrate from each flask was counted on the gamma counter⁸. This counting was treated as final counting, C_f. The initial counting, C_i was taken with blank solution in which the resin was not taken. For Beta countings, the 2 ml portion of the filtrate or the blank was dried over a red lamp in a planchet and counted on Beta counter. The Kd value was then calculated as

$$Kd = \frac{C_i - C_f}{C_f} \times 50 \text{ (ml/g)}$$

The separations were achieved by column equilibrium method. In this method, a 4 cm column (i.d. 0.8 cm) was packed with the resin. After conditioning, the column was eluted with 2 ml fractions of eluent at a flow rate of 10 ml/h. The collected fractions were then counted and converted into the concentrations.

Results and Discussion

The curves in Fig. 1 show some interesting aspects.

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Fig. 1. A plot of log distribution coefficient at different molarity of ammonium thiocyanate.

- (a) Total adsorption in case of Fe(III) and In(III).
- (b) Steady increase in adsorption with thiocyanate concentrations in case of Ag(I) and Hg(II).
- (c) The increase in adsorption with thiocyanate concentrations, reach a maxima and then become constant.
- (d) Slight adsorption in case of Tl(I).
- (e) The case of Cr(III) whose behaviour is different from the rest.

The thiocyanate ion produces a series of negatively charged complexes with the metal ion according to the following reaction :

The basic theoretical approach of Marcus and Coryell¹¹ states that the distribution coefficient of a tracer metal between the aqueous and resin phase is a function of the ligand concentration and the stability of the various complex species. Due to the maintenance of overall charge neutrality it is assumed that the species added to the resin is effectively the neutral complex. The following is the reaction equation :

As the thiocyanate ion concentration is increased the normal effect of resin invasion on the graph is to inhibit the decline of the log distribution values after reaching some peak. This observation may be explained by the secondary cation effect which was treated by Horne¹⁵ for the Zn-Cl-Dowex 1x8 system. As ammonium is the secondary cation in the present case, it causes no difference at low salt concentration. However, at higher concentration, the association of the secondary cation with a resin invasion is strong. Such associated complexes are too large to enter the resin. In case of Cr(III), the desorption of the resin due to ionic association of secondary cation with the anionic chromium complex is possible, giving rise to even less chromium on the resin.

The curves in Fig. 2 show a sharp decrease in Kd values as the percentage of DMSO increases.

Fig. 2. A plot of log distribution coefficients vs volume per cent, DMSO at overall concentration of 1 molar ammonium thiocyanate.

It may be explained on the facts that the donor properties of DMSO are slightly lower than that of thiocyanate. Hence the metal may undergo auto-complex formation in DMSO as :

The case of cobalt was discussed by Gutmann¹⁶ in detail in which he has presumed that an octahedral complex $Co(NCS)(DMSO)_5^+$ is formed according to the reaction :

It means, therefore, that with an increase of DMSO in the system the concentration of positive cobalt complex increases, thus resulting in the low adsorption of the metal ion on resin.

Based on these distribution studies few separations were tried, as a result some important separations have been achieved which are, summarized in Table I.

TABLE I—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES ON DOWEX MACROPOROUS RESIN, MSA-1 COLUMNS (i.d., 4.0×0.8 cm) WITH ELUENT FLOW RATE OF 0.2 ml PER MINUTE

Metal Ions Separated	Taken μg	Found* μg	Eluent	Volume ml
Tl(I)-	202.4	202.3±0.20	E3	50
In(III)	50.8	50.8±0.05	E4	20
Tl(I)-	40.5	40.5±0.05	E3	26
In(III)	203.2	202.2±0.15	E1	40
Tl(I)-	202.4	202.3±0.20	E3	50
Zn(II)	65.0	65.1±0.05	E1	24
Tl(I)-	40.5	40.5±0.05	E3	26
Zn(II)	260.0	260±0.15	E1	40
Tl(I)-	240.5	240.5±0.15	E3	50
Cd(II)	112.5	112.5±0.12	E4	20
Tl(I)	40.5	40.5±0.05	E3	26
Cd(II)	250.0	250.0±0.30	E4	36
Tl(I)-	240.5	240.5±0.25	E3	50
Hg(II)	40.0	40.0±0.10	E1	24
Tl(I)-	40.5	40.5±0.10	E3	26
Hg(II)	400.0	400.0±0.15	E1	45
Mn(II)-	110.0	110.0±0.20	E3	36
Co(II)	110.0	110.0±0.25	E1	60
Mn(II)-	110.0	110.0±0.20	E3	35
Fe(III)	140.0	140.0±0.15	E1	45

* Mean of triplicate determinations with calculated standard deviation.

E1—1.0M NH₄SCN—80%DMSO, 0.5M HCl—60%DMSO
E3—0.05M NH₄SCN ; 0.05 EDTA.

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Decomposition of Alcohols over Ceria

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EXTENSIVE studies have been made on the decomposition of alcohols over alumina and thoria catalysts¹⁻³ and it is observed that they act as dehydration catalysts both for cyclic and acyclic alcohols. The literature survey on this aspect is scanty⁴ and the previous results are all patented. We report in this note, the decomposition of menthol and the substituted pentanols over ceria catalysts obtained by different preparative routes.

Experimental

Three types of catalysts namely, ceria-I, ceria-II and ceria-III were obtained by air-heating for 8 hours at 800°, freshly prepared Ce(OH)₄ and Ce(C₂O₄) and AnalaR Ce(NO₃)₄.2NH₄NO₃.2H₂O respectively. The X-ray powder patterns of the catalyst samples were taken using a Debye-Scherrer Camera of 11.46 cm diam. and CuK_α radiation. The specific surface area measurements of the catalysts were obtained by volumetric method⁵ using nitrogen gas as the sorbate at liquid nitrogen temperature and using BET equation. A flow-type catalytic reactor was employed for the decomposition reactions of alcohols, with the weights of the catalysts, the temperature and the flow-rate being constant. The analyses of the products of alcohol decomposition over ceria catalysts were carried out using Varian 700 VA and 1800 VA gas chromatographs.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the three ceria samples are quite identical and the d_{hkl} values (Å), 3.12s, 2.71m, 1.92s, 1.64s ; 1.57w, 1.36w, 1.25w and